

Developing an Information Model of Manufacturing Process for Sustainability

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Abstract : Manufacturing companies use life-cycle inventory databases to analyze sustainability of their manufacturing processes. Life cycle inventory data provides reference data which may not be accurate for a specific company. Collecting accurate data of manufacturing processes for a specific company requires enormous time and efforts. An information model of typical manufacturing processes can reduce time and efforts to get appropriate reference data for a specific company. This paper shows an attempt to build an abstract information model which can be used to develop information models for specific manufacturing processes.

Keywords : process information model, sustainability, OWL, manufacturing

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